

(Table 2); data were recorded for plant regeneration after 4 wk.

We conclude that an efficient plant regeneration system has been obtained from embryogenic calli of javanica cultivars Rojolele KA and Caping Gajah despite earlier claims that javanicas are resistant to tissue culture.

Bialaphos-resistant calli expressing *gus-A* gene resulting from bombardment experiments were obtained from indica rice cultivars Gajah Mungkur and Maninjau (data not shown). Scoring of *gus* transient expression of rice calli infected with *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain EHA 101 (pIG121Hm) gave a high percentage of *gus* positive calli. We are now growing these calli on medium containing hygromycin to obtain stable transformed material.

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Variation among plants, regenerated from microspore-derived cell suspension protoplasts of rice

Rice embryo and microspore-derived calli are suitable for establishing embryogenic cell suspensions from which protoplast preparations can be readily isolated, engineered, and regenerated to plants. In that aim, somaclonal variation should be minimized. However, ploidy, chromosomal, morphological, and molecular changes have been extensively reported in plants regenerated from embryo callus-cell suspension protoplasts and their progenies.

We recently reported variation in ploidy level among plants regenerated from microspore-derived, haploid cell suspension protoplasts of japonica rice cultivar Miara (Guiderdoni and Chair 1992), as well as a high frequency of agronomical changes in progenies of the diploid protoclines generated in that study (Mézenecv et al 1995). To determine whether the importance of this variation is related to the genotype rather than to our haploid protoplast-

to-diploid plant system, we conducted ploidy analyses and field evaluation among plants regenerated from haploid protoplasts of the temperate japonica cultivar Ariete, the top rice variety in Italy and France.

Flow cytometric analyses of nuclei isolated from protoplast preparations of two and three 4-mo-old cell suspensions established from microspore-derived calli of cultivars Miara and Ariete, respectively permitted detection of haploid nuclei in four suspensions and a mixture of haploid and diploid nuclei in two suspensions (Table 1). We later found ploidy to remain stable over culture periods of up to 18 mo in fully haploid cell suspensions, whereas the haploid to diploid cell ratio varied among suspension cells exhibiting two ploidy levels.

Protoplasts isolated from haploid suspensions yielded a majority of diploid plants whereas the majority of plants derived from suspensions consisting of both haploid and diploid cells exhibited ploidy levels superior or equal to 4n. Distribution of ploidy levels was similar among plants derived from haploid protoplasts of cultivars Miara and Ariete. This was consistent with our previous findings that attributed ploidy changes to early polyploidization events during protoplast culture (Guiderdoni and Chair 1992).

R1 progenies of 72 diploid plants derived from haploid protoplasts of variety Ariete (A4 cell suspension)

Table 1. Ploidy of plants regenerated from microspore-derived cell suspension protoplasts of cultivars Miara and Ariete.

Genotype	Cell suspension	Ploidy level at time of isolation	Samples analyzed (no.) ^a	Frequency of plants exhibiting a ploidy level of					
				n	2n	3n	4n	5n	≥6n
Miara	M1 ^b	n	422	2.1	59.9	12.6	24.4	0.9	0
	M2	n	65	1.5	60.2	21.5	13.8	0	3.0
	M3	n+2n	75	0	10.7	1.3	24.0	12.0	52.0
Ariete	A4 ^a	n	59	1.7	50.9	13.5	30.5	3.4	0
	A4 ^a	n	113	2.5	59.5	17.1	14.4	1.0	5.5
	A6	n	57	1.8	43.8	3.5	38.6	5.3	7
	A7	n+2n	60	10.0	15.0	1.7	28.3	1.7	43.3
Thaibonnet	TB1 ^c	2n	74	0	74.3	2.7	18.9	1.4	2.7

^aResults of two experiments, 4 and 10 mo after initiation of the cell suspension. ^bMean data from 4 experiments (from Guiderdoni and Chair 1992). ^cSeed embryo-callus-derived cell suspension (diploid control).

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation for six traits in the population of protoclonal lines compared with control lines.

Trait	Control lines		Protoclonal lines		Significance of the differences at 5% level (Fisher t test)	Miara protoclonal lines/Miara control lines ^b
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Days to flowering	91.1	1.4	88.7	1.8	NS ^a	Later**
Fertile tillers (8 plants)	64.6	16.2	67.9	13.7	NS	Fewer**
Plant height (cm)	98.1	2.8	89.9	6.5	S	Taller**
Panicle length (cm)	17.3	0.3	18.9	1.2	NS	Longer**
Grain length (mm)	9.1	0.12	9.4	0.22	NS	No difference
Grain width (cm)	2.9	0.06	2.9	0.07	NS	Wider**

^aNS due to difference in earliness between the two replicated experimental plots. ^bFrom Mézencev et al (1995); ** = significant at the 1% level.

were scored for six traits along with control lines in a replicated field experiment (Table 2). Overall, the range of variation observed among the Ariete protoclonal lines was much narrower than that in the protoclonal population generated from Miara following the same experimental procedures, though it remained for most traits wider than that of the control line population.

A unidirectional drift toward earlier, shorter, and longer grained lines was observed. The mean of the protoclonal lines differed significantly from that of the control lines for plant height, and 22 and 44% of the lines exhibited significantly shorter culms and longer grains, respectively. On the other hand, we found no significant difference in fertile tillering, grain width, and panicle length between protoclonal and control lines.

This limited occurrence of variation among the protoclonal lines contrasts with our previous results from evaluating Miara protoclones in the field (Table 2). These findings, along with the analyses of other reports, confirm that the range, direction, and frequency of variation is more related to the genotype than to a given tissue culture procedure.

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AC, with long, slender grains) and japonica (highly responsive to AC, with short, thick grains) genotypes. We examined F₁ (and their corresponding reciprocal), F₂, and BC populations with one BC to each parent. The cosegregation of AC response and grain type was evaluated.

The diallel study indicated that the low AC response shows incomplete dominance with respect to the high response. Thus, the AC response in the F₁ generation is below that of the most responsive parent (Table 1). Possible maternal effects—although not statistically different—were only noted in the crosses when CT8707 was used as the nonresponsive parent (Table 1). The generation mean analyses suggest that simple (oligogenic) genetic systems of different sets of genes control callus induction and green plant regeneration. For callus induction, additive and dominant effects were highly significant, whereas for green plant regeneration, only additive effects were statistically significant (Table 2).

The cosegregation analyses indicate that callus induction ($c^2 = 0.853$) and green plant regeneration ($c^2 = 0.978$)

Table 1. Anther culture response of crosses between japonicas CT6241-17-1-5-1 and Todoroki Wase, and indicas IR43 and CT8707.^a

Parent or cross	Callus anther ⁻¹ (%)		Green plants callus ⁻¹ (%)	
IR43	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT8707	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT6241	19.8	b	43.9	a
Todoroki Wase	42.2	a	28.8	b
IR43/CT8707	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT8707/IR43	0.0	d	0.0	d
CT6241/Todoroki	58.3	a	28.3	ab
Todoroki/CT6241	65.2	a	23.2	ab
CT8707/Todoroki	2.2	bcd	0.0	d
Todoroki/CT8707	15.9	bc	3.3	cd
CT8707/CT6241	6.6	bcd	3.3	cd
CT6241/CT8707	11.8	bcd	0.0	d
IR43/Todoroki	15.4	b	12.3	bc
Todoroki/IR43	17.9	b	12.8	b
Todoroki/IR43 F ₂	12.7	bc	11.7	b
Todoroki/IR43//IR43	5.2	c	7.2	c
Todoroki/IR43//Todoroki	24.9	b	17.6	b
IR43/CT6241	13.9	bc	11.9	bc
CT6241/IR43	13.4	bc	22.1	b
CT6241/IR43 F ₂	4.5	cd	7.5	b
CT6241/IR43//IR43	5.4	c	7.9	b
CT6241/IR43//CT6241	12.3	bc	15.9	b

^aMeans with the same letter are not significantly different according to the Waller-Duncan K-ratio test, $p \leq 50.01$.

Toward introgression of high response to anther culture into indica rices

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Anther culture (AC) is routinely used in our program to reduce the generation time for broadening the genetic diversity of breeding gene pools and to facilitate molecular tagging of genes. Most of these applications have been mainly restrained to crosses containing at least one japonica parent due to the recalcitrance of indica genotypes.

Replacing sucrose with maltose and adding silver nitrate to the callus induction medium substantially increases the AC response of indicas (Lentini et al 1995); however, the yield of doubled haploids per anther from indicas is still about 20-fold less than that from japonicas. Evidence exists that a few genes control AC response in rice (Miah et al 1985, Quimio and Zapata 1990). Therefore, the introgression of the high AC response from japonicas into indicas could facilitate applying AC as a routine tool for breeding indica rice.

We conducted diallel and backcross (BC) inheritance analyses using crosses between true indica (nonresponsive to